

Control-oriented modeling and observation of a single cell proton ceramic electrochemical reactor for single-stage ammonia cracking to compressed hydrogen

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ABSTRACT

A novel proton ceramic electrochemical reactor has recently been proposed for the efficient extraction of hydrogen from ammonia. This reactor integrates heat management, ammonia dehydrogenation, hydrogen separation, and compression into a single, streamlined process. Despite its potential, the operation and monitoring of the reactor pose significant challenges. Effective management of the complex nonlinear interactions between electrical, chemical, and thermal processes is essential to avoid performance degradation and ensure safe operation of this new electrochemical reactor. Our contributions are a first step for addressing these challenges through two key innovations. First, we introduce a control-oriented, and computationally efficient model for a single cell of the electrochemical reactor. Second, we leverage this model to develop a soft sensor based on observer theory, that uses real-time measurements to estimate the hydrogen mass fraction and the partial pressures of hydrogen at both sides of the ceramic membrane and the membrane area specific resistance.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen, as an energy carrier, has been established as a key element in the current energy transition. Such statement is justified by the potential of hydrogen in strategic sectors such as electric vehicles [1] or building energy management systems [2]. In terms of hydrogen generation, a combination of wind and solar energy with processes such as water electrolysis are the preferred methods in order to produce green hydrogen with minimal greenhouse emissions [3]. However, the renewable energy sources and the electrolysis systems should operate as many hours as possible in order to compete with more conventional (but not environmentally friendly) hydrogen production methods. This fact makes green hydrogen production strongly dependable on specific favorable environment and/or geographical conditions. Consequently, there exist preferred locations for the generation of green hydrogen [4], which are not uniformly distributed throughout the world [5]. Considering this, the need of transporting green hydrogen between international borders will become increasingly important as the use of hydrogen increases in the economy, especially in regions with low renewable energy potential.

From low to medium distances, transport of hydrogen in gaseous form through pipelines has been proven to be economically and environmentally feasible [6]. Nonetheless, alternative transport methods become more feasible if one requires transporting hydrogen for long distances, specifically considering marine transport [7,8]. These alternatives include: liquefying hydrogen [9] or bonding the hydrogen with other molecules to generate hydrogen carriers such as liquid organic hydrogen carriers [10], CO₂ neutral carriers [11] (combined with CO₂ sequestration mechanisms) and ammonia [12]. Each alternative has its own advantages and disadvantages. Nonetheless, ammonia stands out as the most preferable option, due to its reasonable cost and the already existence of infrastructure for transport and storage of ammonia [13].

The most widespread method for extracting hydrogen from ammonia follows a multi-stage process. First, a thermal catalytic reaction separates the ammonia through a dehydrogenation process ($\text{NH}_3 \rightarrow 1/2\text{N}_2 + 3/2\text{H}_2$). This reaction is endothermic and, usually, requires the use of fuel combustion as a heat source. Second, this reaction is coupled with a downstream separation process using e.g. pressure swing adsorption [14] and subsequent mechanical compression. This

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multi-stage process usually suffers from energy losses which have to be partially recovered by utilizing centralized large scale processes [15]. This fact makes infeasible the deployment of distributed processes where hydrogen comes from an ammonia carrier.

Alternatively, ammonia dehydrogenation and hydrogen separation can be achieved simultaneously by means of hydrogen selective membranes. Usually, membranes used for ammonia dehydrogenation are metallic and based on Pd alloys [16]. Unfortunately, in such processes, the hydrogen separation from the rest of species is driven by a partial pressure difference across the membrane. Thus, the hydrogen produced is of low pressure and subsequent mechanical compression has to be implemented, which increases the cost and the energy consumption.

On the other hand, simultaneous hydrogen separation and compression can be achieved electrochemically with proton conducting ceramic membranes, being Y-doped BaZrO₃ – BaCeO₃ solid solutions (referred here as BZCY) prominent examples. These type of membrane are stable and functional over a wide range of chemical conditions and temperatures [15,17,18]. Systems that extract pure hydrogen from gas mixtures by electrochemically pumping protons through a ceramic membrane are usually called proton ceramic electrochemical reactors (PCERs).

A novel PCER has been proposed in [19] which combines heat integration, ammonia dehydrogenation, hydrogen separation and compression in a single step. In this solution, the dehydrogenating reaction is produced in the inner side of a ceramic tube, the generated hydrogen is then separated and compressed through a dense ceramic proton conducting membrane by means of applying electricity. This process gives increased ammonia conversion and heat generation due to the ohmic losses. The thermal coupling between the endothermic dehydrogenation and exothermic Joule heating from the ohmic losses avoids needing external heat sources to sustain the operation.

Although there is great potential in the PCER proposed in [19], there are still some concerns that should be addressed. In particular, concerns related to the monitoring and operation of the device. Indeed, the device couples complex nonlinear electrical, chemical and thermal processes which, if not properly managed, can lead to performance degradation and safety issues. This motivates designing control algorithms for optimally and safely operating the PCER. Nonetheless, the design of most control algorithm requires a mathematical model that describes the dynamics of the system. In this sense, not all models are adequate; we require models that are oriented to control design. This, on the one hand, implies the need of models described by low dimension ordinary differential equations. Models of large dimension or described by partial differential equations usually end-up in intractable analysis from a control point-of-view. On the other hand, a control-oriented model needs to be computationally efficient, since most control algorithms require the model to be run in real-time and in parallel to the device. Considering these constraints, it is clear that the model used in the original publication [19] cannot be used for control design. With this in mind, the main purpose of this work is to develop a control-oriented model of a single cell single-stage PCER [19].

Additionally, most control algorithms require real-time information of internal variables of the device. These internal variables cannot always be measured, due to technical, economical and financial constraints, which may limit the number and type of sensors in the device. Considering this, the second objective of this work is to utilize the proposed control-oriented model to develop an algorithm, referred here as soft-sensor or observer, to estimate some of the internal variables of the system. In particular, we present and validate an algorithm to estimate in real-time the hydrogen partial pressure in the internal channel and the corrected area specific resistance of the membrane at nominal conditions.

The remaining part of this work is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the considered PCER and presents the control-oriented model. Section 3 compares the proposed model with a more computational expensive multi-physics model based on [19]. Section 4 presents and

Fig. 1. Scheme of a single cell of the PCER presented in [19]. The internal electrode is composed by nickel and a proton-conducting material BZCY. The electrolyte consists of a dense layer of BZCY. The external electrode is a porous layer also composed of nickel and BZCY.

validates an algorithm to estimate in real time the hydrogen partial pressure in the internal channel and the corrected area specific resistance of the membrane at nominal conditions. Finally, some conclusions are drawn in Section 5. All the nomenclature of the work is summarized in Table 1.

2. Mathematical model

2.1. PCER description

In this work, we consider a single 4 cm-long electrochemical cell of the device presented in [19]. As depicted in Fig. 1, the device consists in two tubular channels, one inside the other. The internal channel is fed with dry ammonia or aqueous ammonia, while the external channel is fed with H₂O.

The internal channel of the cell is supported by a porous layer composed of nickel and a proton-conducting material BZCY. The nickel in the internal support serves a dual purpose: it acts as an electronic conductor within the electrochemical system and as a catalyst for the ammonia dehydrogenation (cracking) reaction, where the ammonia is separated following the next reaction

Following the internal electrode there is an electrolyte that consists of a dense 20–30 μm layer of BZCY. The outer electrode is a porous layer of the same thickness, also composed of nickel and BZCY. Hydrogen generated by the ammonia dehydrogenation reaction is separated from the rest of species, compressed and transferred between the internal and external channel through the electrochemical compression process of the electrochemical cell. Precisely, the hydrogen electrochemical compression reaction begins at the anode side where the hydrogen is separated into protons and electrons

Then, the protons are transported through the (H⁺)-conducting ceramic electrolyte, while the electrons are transported through an external circuit. Then, in the cathode side, the protons and electrons combined again to generate H₂, which is then released into the external channel.

We highlight that, while the ammonia dehydrogenation reaction is endothermic the hydrogen electrochemical compression is an exothermic process. This opens the possibility of operating the device at net endothermic or exothermic depending on the degree of ammonia reaction and H₂ separation and compression throughout the cell.

Table 1
Nomenclature.

Symbol	Description	Units
Model variables		
ρ_q	Gas density in the channel q	kg m ⁻³
$y_{i,q}$	Mass fraction of the species i in the volume q	kg kg ⁻¹
$p_{i,q}$	Partial pressure of the species i in volume q	Pa
T_{cell}	Cell temperature	K
T_i	Temperature of the species i	K
$\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$	Inlet flow of the species i at the channel q	kg s ⁻¹
$\dot{m}_{q,i}^O$	Outlet flow of the species i at the channel q	kg s ⁻¹
$\dot{m}_{q,i,s}$	Mass flows related to the source/sink terms	kg s ⁻¹
Q_q^O	Outlet volumetric flow	m ³ s ⁻¹
ΔP_q	Pressure differential in the channel q	Pa
P_q^0	Outlet pressure volume q	Pa
$T_{in,q}$	Inlet temperature volume q	K
I_{mem}	Membrane current density	A m ⁻²
R_i	Ammonia decomposition reaction of the species i	kg s ⁻¹
k_b	Arrhenius equation decomposition reaction	mol kg ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
ξ_r	Partial pressure correction factor	–
χ_r	Active mass correction term	kg
$\Delta\Phi_{mem}$	Cell Voltage	V
E_{rev}	Reversible potential	V
\tilde{E}_{rev}	Reversible voltage at equilibrium	V
η_{ohm}	Ohmic losses	V
ASR	Corrected area specific resistance	Ω m ²
E	Thermal Energy	J
$\dot{Q}_{in/out}$	Source/sinks of thermal energy	W
Model parameters		
r_q	Effective radius of the volume q	m
L_q	Length of the volume q	m
V_q	Volume of the control volume q	m
ΔR	Eff. radial distance channel/porous media	m
A_{shell}	Ambient contact area	m ²
A_{mem}	Cell area	m ²
A_q	Cross-sectional area of the volume q	m ²
μ	Viscosity of the gas composition	Pa s
D_i	Diffusivity coefficient in Porous media of the species i	m ² s ⁻¹
ϵ	Porosity of the porous media	–
$E_{a,r}$	Activation energy of the reaction	J mol ⁻¹
k_b^0	Kinetic pre-exponential factor	mol kg ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
$K_{i,0}$	NH ₃ reaction constant at standard conditions	Pa ⁻¹
$Q_{i,0}$	NH ₃ reaction constant temp. correction term	J mol ⁻¹
f_{Ni}	Mass fraction of Ni	–
f_u	Fraction of active Ni	–
ASR^0	ASR at nominal conditions	Ω m ²
E_{mem}	Apparent activation energy of membrane	J mol ⁻¹
$M_b c_{p,b}$	Specific heat capacity solid phase multiplied by mass	J K ⁻¹
$c_{p,i}$	Specific heat capacity of the specie i	J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
h_{ca}	Ambient heat transfer coefficient	W m ⁻² K ⁻¹
ΔH_r	Enthalpy of the ammonia dec. reaction	J mol ⁻¹
T_{amb}	Ambient temperature	K
R	Ideal gas constant	J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
F	Faraday constant	C mol ⁻¹
M_i	Molar mass species i	kg mol ⁻¹
Observer variables		
x	State vector	–
y	Measured output	–
u	Input vector	–
\hat{x}	State estimation vector	–
\mathcal{X}	State vector set	–
\mathcal{U}	Input vector set	–
k_i	State space model parameter	–
$\hat{p}_{H_2,q}$	Partial pressure estimation of hydrogen in volume q	Pa
u_c	Nominal current value	A
s_b	High-frequency current term	A
κ	Scaling term	–
ϵ	Frequency scaling term	–
Ψ	Regressor vector	–
θ	Unknown parameter vector	–
$\hat{\theta}$	Unknown parameter estimation	–
η	Parameter estimator filter state	–
Ω	Parameter estimator transition matrix	–
y_{pd}	Measured output post-filter	–

(continued on next page)

Table 1 (continued).

Symbol	Description	Units
Ψ_{pd}	Regressor vector post-filter	–
α	Persistence of excitation lower bound	–
Γ	Adaptation gain estimator	–
$\mathcal{O}(\cdot)$	Approximation error	V

Table 2
Solution variables at each control volume.

Control volume	ρ [kg m ⁻³]	y_{NH_3} [kg kg ⁻¹]	y_{H_2} [kg kg ⁻¹]	y_{N_2} [kg kg ⁻¹]	T_{cell} [K]
Gas Channel Dec. Side	✓Eq. (3)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (28)
BZCY/Ni Porous media	✓Eq. (3)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (12)	✓Eq. (28)
Gas Channel Sweep Side	✓Eq. (3)		✓Eq. (12)		✓Eq. (28)

Fig. 2. Graphical depiction of the model control volumes. The terms $m_{I,i}$ and $m_{O,i}$ depicts the mass flow of the species that enter and leave, respectively, the control volumes. \dot{R}_{A_1} depicts the dehydrogenation reaction. \dot{R}_{H_2} is the flux of hydrogen compressed and transported across the membrane. Finally, the electrical model depicts the potential associated to the electrochemical compression.

2.2. Model description

In this work, we develop a pseudo-1D model for the PCER. Precisely, we will approximate the distributed nature of the cell by coupling 3 control volumes. The first control volume represents the gas channel at the decomposition side. The second control volume is the gas channel at the sweep side. Finally, the third control volume is the porous media at the decomposition side. We will ignore the porous media at the sweep side since its dimension and effect on the overall dynamics of the system is order of magnitudes lower than the one in the decomposition side. The control volumes are depicted in Fig. 2.

In the decomposition side gas channel and the BZCY/Ni porous media, there will co-exist NH_3 , H_2 , H_2O and N_2 , while in the sweep side gas channel there will only be H_2O and H_2 . In each control volume we will solve for the mass fraction of each species, density of the gas mixture and the temperature. Table 2 summarizes the variables that are being solved at each control volume. Notice that we do not solve for the mass fraction of H_2O since it can be deduced from the rest of mass fractions. This will make the model have a total mass conservation.

Finally, in the next list we summarize the main assumptions that will apply in all control volumes.

- We neglect the effect of the gravity in the fluid dynamics.
- Gas mixtures are assumed to be isobaric and ideal.
- We consider that the fluids are incompressible, but with varying density.

Particular assumptions of each control volume will be explained in the next sections.

2.3. Gas channel sub-model

In the PCER, we consider two gas channels. One on the reforming/decomposition side (where NH_3 is introduced) and another for the

sweep side (where H_2 is extracted). We will consider the following assumptions:

- The input mass flow rates and input species mass fraction are specified as a boundary condition in the inlet.
- The outlet pressure is fixed as a boundary condition.
- The mass fluxes in the longitudinal coordinate (of the single cell) are constrained to be convection-only (zero diffusive flux).
- The mass flux in the radial coordinate is only diffusive (zero convective flux).

Considering these assumptions, the mass rate of change in the gas channel control volume will be characterized by the convective flux in and out of the channel and the rate of change due to source/sinks terms. These source/sink terms will account for the diffusion between the channel at the decomposition side and the BZCY/Ni porous media and the separation/compression of hydrogen through the ceramic membrane.

As the control volume is zero-dimensional in the space domain, the density within the channel and the source/sink terms are assumed to be uniform in all the control volume. The mass balance in the gas channel is therefore derived as:

$$V_q \frac{\partial \rho_q}{\partial t} = \sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i}^I - \sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i}^O + \sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i,s} \quad (3)$$

where the sub-index q refers to the channel q (decomposition or sweep) and the sub-index i refers to the species (NH_3 , H_2 , H_2O or N_2). The term V_q [m³] refers to the volume of the channel q , ρ_q [kg m⁻³] is the gas density in the channel q , $\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$ [kg s⁻¹] is the inlet flow of the species i at the channel q , $\dot{m}_{q,i}^O$ [kg s⁻¹] is the outlet flow of the same species and $\dot{m}_{q,i,s}$ [kg s⁻¹] depicts the mass flows related to the source/sink terms.

2.3.1. Input mass flows $\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$

We assume that all the terms $\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$ are fixed as an input to the model. Specifically, we will fix the total mass flow and the species mass fraction as a boundary condition in the inlet.

2.3.2. Output mass flows $\dot{m}_{q,i}^O$

The outlet mass flow is driven by the pressure differential between the channel and the external environment. The pressure differential is characterized as a Poiseuille flow for laminar regimes in a tube. That is, the average flow rate, Q_q^O [m³ s⁻¹] in the channel q is computed as

$$Q_q^O = \frac{\Delta P_q \pi r_q^4}{8 L_q \mu_q}, \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta P_q = P_q - P_q^0$ [Pa] is the pressure differential between the control volume pressure P_q [Pa] and the control volume outlet pressure P_q^0 [Pa], r_q [m] is the effective radius of the tube,¹ L_q [m] is the channel length

¹ This is a directly measurable variable. However, if unknown, it can be computed as $\sqrt{\frac{A_q}{\pi}}$, where A_q is the cross-sectional area of the tube.

and μ_q [Pa s] is the viscosity of the gas.² Then, the total outlet mass flow can be computed as

$$\sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i}^O = \rho_q Q_q^O. \quad (5)$$

2.3.3. Source terms $\dot{m}_{q,i,s}$ gas channels

The source terms $\dot{m}_{dec,i,s}$ at the decomposition side account for the mass transfer between the channel and the porous media. This mass transfer is assumed to be purely diffusive. Precisely, each individual mass flow is derived by combining the continuity equation with Fick's law

$$\dot{m}_{dec,i,s} = -V_{dec} D_i \nabla \cdot (\nabla \cdot y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}) = -V_{dec} D_i \Delta \cdot y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}, \quad (6)$$

where D_i [m² s⁻¹] is the diffusivity coefficient of the species i and $y_{i,dec}$ [kg kg⁻¹] is the mass fraction of the species i in the decomposition channel. In this work, we assume the diffusivity coefficient to be constant and to already account for the porosity of the BZCY/Ni media. Naturally, a more precise model could be achieved by correcting the diffusivity considering the gas mixture. However, such correction has been obviated in order to simplify the model.

We recall here two assumptions of the model. First, that all the control volumes are assumed to be cylindrical. Second, we only have diffusion in the radial coordinate. Considering these two assumptions, defining r as the radial coordinate of the cylinder, the divergence term $\Delta \cdot y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}$ is computed as

$$\Delta \cdot y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec} = \frac{1}{r_{dec}} \left(\frac{\partial y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}}{\partial r} \right) + \left(\frac{\partial^2 y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}}{\partial r^2} \right), \quad (7)$$

where r_{dec} [m] is the effective radius of the decomposition side channel. Since we defined the full gas channel as a single control volume, the term $\frac{\partial y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}}{\partial r}$ is only computed through the boundary condition between the gas channel and the porous media. That is,

$$\frac{\partial y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}}{\partial r} = \frac{y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec} - y_{i,pm} \rho_{pm}}{\Delta R}, \quad \frac{\partial^2 y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}}{\partial r^2} = 0, \quad (8)$$

where $\Delta R = r_{pm} - r_{dec}$ [m] is the radial distance between the gas channel and the porous media control volumes, r_{pm} [m] is the effective radius of the porous media and $y_{i,pm}$ and ρ_{pm} are the mass fraction of the specie i and the gas density in the porous media, respectively.

In conclusion, the diffusive flux of each species between the decomposition side gas channel and the porous media can be computed as

$$\dot{m}_{dec,i,s} = \frac{V_{dec} D_i}{r_{dec} \Delta R} (y_{i,pm} \rho_{pm} - y_{i,dec} \rho_{dec}). \quad (9)$$

We recall here that the diffusive terms only appear in the gas channel of the decomposition side. At the sweep side, the porous media and its associated diffusive flux are obviated. Nonetheless, the sweep side contains an additional source term that accounts for the hydrogen transported and compressed through the BZCY membrane.

Precisely, we have a separation of H₂ from the rest of the species due to the electrochemical compression process at the BZCY membrane. The H₂ flux is coupled with the membrane current density. Specifically, there is the following source term in the sweep side gas channel related to the hydrogen flux through the membrane:

$$\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2,s} = \frac{M_{H_2} I_{mem} A_{mem}}{2F}, \quad (10)$$

where I_{mem} [A m⁻²] is the membrane current density and A_{mem} [m²] is the membrane area.

² An average of the temperature-corrected viscosities of all species has been used to compute this value. A more accurate model could be obtained by dynamically accounting for the temperature-dependent viscosity of each individual species and computing the mixture viscosity using the Wilke method.

2.3.4. Individual species dynamics

In relation to the dynamics of each individual specie, the computation is treated in a similar fashion as the density within the channel volume. That is convective flux will again be integrated over the cross-sectional area to give a sum of input and output mass fluxes and source/sink terms.

$$V_q \frac{\partial \rho_{q,i}}{\partial t} = \dot{m}_{q,i}^I - \dot{m}_{q,i}^O + \dot{m}_{q,i,s}, \quad (11)$$

where $\rho_{q,i}$ is the density of the species i in the channel q . Nonetheless, for the control purpose of the model, it is more convenient to directly work with the mass fraction of each species i , denoted here as $y_{i,q}$. To compute the dynamics of the mass fraction, we are going to use the chain rule over the equality $V_q \rho_{q,i} = V_q y_{i,q} \rho_q$. By differentiating both sides of this equality, using (11) and isolating the $V_q \rho_q \frac{\partial y_{q,i}}{\partial t}$ term we get the following equation

$$V_q \rho_q \frac{\partial y_{q,i}}{\partial t} = -V_q y_{q,i} \frac{\partial \rho_q}{\partial t} + \dot{m}_{q,i}^I - \dot{m}_{q,i}^O + \dot{m}_{q,i,s}. \quad (12)$$

Finally, once we have the mass fraction of each species and the total density in the channel, we can obtain the partial pressure of each species through the ideal gas law

$$p_{i,q} = \frac{y_{q,i} \rho_q R T_{cell}}{M_i}, \quad (13)$$

where p_i [Pa] is the partial pressure of the species i in volume q , R [J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹] is the ideal gas constant, T_{cell} [K] is the cell temperature and M_i [Kg mol] is the molar mass of the species i .

2.4. BZCY/Ni porous media sub-model

In the porous media, the mass balance is composed by three terms

$$\epsilon V_q \frac{\partial \rho_{pm}}{\partial t} = -\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2,s} - \sum_i \dot{m}_{dec,i,s} + \sum_i \dot{R}_i, \quad (14)$$

where ϵ [-] is the porosity of the control volume and \dot{R}_i [kg s⁻¹] is a term that comes from the ammonia decomposition reaction.

Specifically, the species may enter/leave the porous media through the diffusion process $\dot{m}_{dec,i,s}$ presented in (9), which has been corrected to account for the porous media volume. Additionally, in the BZCY/Ni porous media we have the two main reactions, the hydrogen electrochemical separation and the ammonia decomposition. The first one is represented by $\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2,s}$ and computed through (10). The second one is explained in the next section.

2.4.1. Decomposition reaction

A source/sink term that comprises the ammonia decomposition is included in the porous media of the decomposition side. The reaction activity was modeled using a kinetic equation which has been fitted for this work. The expression takes the following form

$$\dot{R}_{A1} = k_b \xi_r \chi_r. \quad (15)$$

The factor k_b is an Arrhenius equation included to account for non-standard temperature conditions in the reaction and is computed as

$$k_b = k_b^0 \exp\left(-\frac{E_{a,r}}{RT_{cell}}\right), \quad (16)$$

where k_b^0 [mol kg⁻¹ s⁻¹] is a pre-exponential kinetic coefficient for the reaction, which already considers specific surface area of the Ni cermet support, and $E_{a,r}$ [J mol⁻¹] is the activation energy of the reaction. The factor ξ_r comprises depends on the partial pressure of the species in the Ni cermet support

$$\xi_r = \frac{K_{NH_3} p_{NH_3}}{\left[1 + K_{NH_3} p_{NH_3} + \sqrt{K_{N_2} p_{N_2}} + \sqrt{K_{H_2} p_{H_2}} + \sqrt{K_{H_2O} p_{H_2O}}\right]^2}, \quad (17)$$

where K_i [Pa^{-1}] is a reaction constant of the specie i which is corrected with the temperature as follows

$$K_i = K_{i,0} \exp \frac{Q_{i,0}}{RT_{cell}}, \quad (18)$$

where $K_{i,0}$ [Pa^{-1}] is the reaction constant of the i_{th} specie at standard conditions and $Q_{i,0}$ [J mol^{-1}] is a temperature correction constant. Finally, the factor χ_r corrects the decomposition reaction rate to the mass of active Ni in the support:

$$\chi_r = f_{Ni} f_u \rho_{Ni} V_{pm}, \quad (19)$$

where f_{Ni} [-] is the fraction of Ni mass on the support, f_u [-] is the fraction of active Ni mass, ρ_{Ni} [kg m^{-3}] is the density of Ni and V_{pm} [m^3] the volume of porous media.

Now, with the ammonia decomposition reaction rate we can compute the species mass source/sink terms at the decomposition side for the porous media control volume. Specifically, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{R}_{H_2} &= 3M_{H_2} \dot{R}_{A1}, \\ \dot{R}_{N_2} &= M_{N_2} \dot{R}_{A1}, \\ \dot{R}_{NH_3} &= -2M_{NH_3} \dot{R}_{A1}. \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

2.4.2. Individual species dynamics

The dynamics of each individual species is computed as in Section 2.3.4.

2.5. Electrical sub-model

The ammonia decomposition reaction is achieved by a purely chemical reaction. Nonetheless, the separation and compression of hydrogen in the BZCY membrane is achieved through an electrochemical process. The potential difference between the anode and cathode across the electrolyte is decomposed into a reversible term given by the Nernst equation and an irreversible term given by the ohmic losses in the membrane electrode assembly. In this model, we assume that the activation overpotentials are incorporated into the ohmic losses. This simplification was also adopted in the original work that motivated this paper [19, Table S4]. By maintaining this assumption, we ensure consistency and enable an adequate comparison between the original multi-physics model and the simplified approach proposed in this paper.

Specifically, the membrane cell voltage, $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$ [V], is computed as

$$\Delta\Phi_{mem} = E_{rev} + \eta_{ohm}. \quad (21)$$

The reversible potential E_{rev} [V] is computed through the Nernst equation

$$E_{rev} = \frac{RT_{cell}}{2F} \ln \left(\frac{p_{H_2, sweep}}{p_{H_2, BZCY}} \right), \quad (22)$$

where $p_{H_2, BZCY}$ [Pa] is the H_2 partial pressure at the porous media control volume and $p_{H_2, sweep}$ [Pa] is the partial pressure at the sweep side. The factor η_{ohm} [V] accounts for the ohmic losses in the membrane, which are corrected considering the membrane temperature and computed as

$$\eta_{ohm} = ASR I_{mem}, \quad (23)$$

where ASR [$\Omega \text{ m}^2$] is the corrected area specific resistance which is computed as

$$ASR = ASR^0 \exp \left(\frac{E_{mem}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_{cell}} - \frac{1}{1073} \right] \right) \quad (24)$$

where ASR^0 [$\Omega \text{ m}^2$] is ASR at nominal conditions (1073 K) and E_{mem} [J mol^{-1}] is the apparent activation energy of the membrane.

2.6. Thermal sub-model

For the thermal sub-model of the system, and with the aim to further simplify the model, we make the following assumptions:

- The temperature in all the cell is uniform. That is, all the control volumes will present the same temperature.
- The reactor's outer boundaries (the external surface of the reactor shell) facilitate heat exchange with a surrounding domain maintained at a fixed operating temperature, simulating a temperature-controlled environment.
- The heat transfer between cell and the exterior is convection-only. We ignore radiation sinks and sources.
- The gases inside the cell have the same temperature as the solid media. Consequently, we do not model the thermal dynamics of each individual species, and we assume that the energy transfer between the gases and the cell structure is instantaneous.

An energy balance is implemented to determine the temperature dynamics of the cell. Precisely, the energy dynamics is equal to the sum of heat sources \dot{Q}_{in} and energy transported by input mass inside the cell, less the heat sinks \dot{Q}_{out} and the energy of the mass transported out of the cell. Let E be the thermal energy of the cell and T_i the temperature of the species i introduced in the system, then:

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = \dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{Q}_{out} + \sum_q \sum_i (\dot{m}_{q,i}^I c_{p,i} T_i - \dot{m}_{q,i}^O c_{p,i} T_{cell}) \quad (25)$$

where q depicts the control volume, $c_{p,i}$ [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$] is the specific heat capacity of the specie i , T_{cell} [K] is the temperature of the cell and T_i [K] is the temperature of the i_{th} species that enters the cell.

Then, to convert the thermal energy E into the temperature of the cell, we are going to apply the chain rule over the equation of the total thermal energy in the cell

$$E = M_b c_{p, cell} T_{cell} + \sum_q \sum_i y_{i,q} \rho_q V_q c_{p,i} T_{cell}, \quad (26)$$

where M_b [Kg] and $c_{p, cell}$ [$\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$] is the mass and heat capacity of the solid media, respectively. Before applying the chain rule, we highlight that the thermal energy stored in the solid is order of magnitudes higher than the one in the gas media. Thus, we can approximate the total thermal energy as $E \approx M_b c_{p, cell} T_{cell}$ and apply the chain rule over this approximation. More precisely, we get

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial t} = M_b c_{p, cell} \frac{\partial T_{cell}}{\partial t}. \quad (27)$$

Combining Eqs. (25) and (27) and isolating the temperature derivative we obtain a differential equation for the temperature dynamics:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial T_{cell}}{\partial t} &= (M_b c_{p, cell})^{-1} \left[\dot{Q}_{in} - \dot{Q}_{out} + \sum_q \sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i}^I c_{p,i} T_i \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \sum_q \sum_i \dot{m}_{q,i}^O c_{p,i} T_{cell} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

The remaining part of this section is dedicated to define the terms \dot{Q}_{in} and \dot{Q}_{out} , which depicts sources and sinks of thermal energy. The main source heat of the reaction is the energy generated by the hydrogen transport through the membrane

$$\dot{Q}_{in} = (ASR I_{mem} + E_{rev}) A_{mem} I_{mem}. \quad (29)$$

The heat sinks are the endothermic ammonia decomposition reaction and the heat dissipated to the ambient from a convection process

$$\dot{Q}_{out} = \Delta H_r \dot{R}_{A1} + h_{ca} A_{shell} (T_{cell} - T_{amb}), \quad (30)$$

where ΔH_r [J mol^{-1}] is the enthalpy of the ammonia decomposition reaction, h_{ca} [$\text{W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$] is the ambient heat transfer coefficient and A_{shell} is the contact surface area of the cell exterior.

Table 3
List of parameters of the model for CFD comparison.

Symbol	Description	Value	Units
Geometry parameters			
r_{sweep}	Effective radius of the sweep side tube	$4.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	m
r_{dec}	Effective radius of the dec. side tube	$3 \cdot 10^{-3}$	m
r_{pm}	Effective radius of the porous media	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	m
L_{cell}	Length of the active cell	0.04	m
L_{dec}	Length of the sweep/dec. side tube	0.12	m
V_{dec}	Volume decomposition side	$2.54 \cdot 10^{-6}$	m ³
V_{sweep}	Volume sweep side	$8.48 \cdot 10^{-7}$	m ³
ΔR	Eff. radial distance channel/porous media	$2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	m
A_{shell}	Ambient contact area	$3.39 \cdot 10^{-2}$	m ²
A_{mem}	Cell area	$16.96 \cdot 10^{-4}$	m ²
Gas Properties			
μ	Viscosity of the gas composition	$3 \cdot 10^{-4}$ [20]	Pa s
D_{N_2}	N ₂ diffusivity coefficient in Porous media	$1.81 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [21]	m ² s ⁻¹
D_{NH_3}	NH ₃ diffusivity coefficient in Porous media	$1.52 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [21]	m ² s ⁻¹
D_{H_2}	H ₂ diffusivity coefficient in Porous media	$1.56 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [21]	m ² s ⁻¹
Porous media properties			
ϵ	Porosity of the porous media	0.25	[-]
Chemical kinetic parameters			
$E_{a,r}$	Activation energy of the reaction	$19.7 \cdot 10^4$ [22]	J mol ⁻¹
k_b^0	Kinetic pre-exponential factor	$2.53 \cdot 10^{14}$	mol kg ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
$K_{NH_3,0}$	NH ₃ reaction constant at standard conditions	$3.62 \cdot 10^{-12}$	Pa ⁻¹
$K_{H_2,0}$	H ₂ reaction constant at standard conditions	$5.38 \cdot 10^{-14}$	Pa ⁻¹
$K_{N_2,0}$	N ₂ reaction constant at standard conditions	$3 \cdot 10^{-11}$	Pa ⁻¹
$K_{H_2O,0}$	H ₂ O reaction constant at standard conditions	$5.13 \cdot 10^{-7}$	Pa ⁻¹
$Q_{NH_3,0}$	NH ₃ reaction constant temp. correction term	98 446	J mol ⁻¹
$Q_{H_2,0}$	H ₂ reaction constant temp. correction term	126 447	J mol ⁻¹
$Q_{N_2,0}$	N ₂ reaction constant temp. correction term	3276	J mol ⁻¹
$Q_{H_2O,0}$	H ₂ O reaction constant temp. correction term	25 200	J mol ⁻¹
f_{Ni}	Mass fraction of Ni	0.5	[-]
f_u	Fraction of active Ni	0.5	[-]
Electrical Parameters			
ASR^0	ASR at nominal conditions	$5 \cdot 10^{-5}$ [19]	Ω m ²
E_{mem}	apparent activation energy of membrane	$4 \cdot 10^4$ [19]	J mol ⁻¹
Thermal Parameters			
$M_b c_{p,b}$	Specific heat capacity solid phase multiplied by mass	5	J K ⁻¹
h_{ca}	Ambient heat transfer coefficient	0	W m ⁻² K ⁻¹
T_{amb}	Ambient temperature	873.15	K

3. Comparison with a multi-physics model

In order to validate the proposed model, we compare the results obtained by the proposed control-oriented model with the ones obtained by a single cell version of the multi-physics modeling presented in [19]. We recall that the purpose of the proposed model is the development of advanced control algorithms. In this sense, it is crucial that the model properly characterizes the correlation between the controllable inputs of the system, and crucial indicators for the adequate operation of the PCER. With this in mind, from a control perspective, the most important inputs of the PCER are:

- The ammonia input mass flow in the decomposition side $\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$.
- The membrane current density, I_{mem} .

Additionally, the indicators of interest, in this work, are:

- The hydrogen extraction ratio: The mass of hydrogen extracted in the sweep side divided by the total hydrogen extracted in the cell, that is

$$H_2 \text{ Extraction} = \frac{\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2}^O}{\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2}^O + \dot{m}_{dec,H_2}^O}. \quad (31)$$

- The H₂ lost in the outlet: The molar fraction of H₂ in the decomposition side gas channel. Computed as

$$H_2 \text{ Lost} = \frac{y_{H_2,dec} M_{H_2}^{-1}}{\sum_i y_{i,dec} M_i^{-1}} \quad (32)$$

- The NH₃ conversion ratio: The ratio between the mass of NH₃ introduced in the system and mass of NH₃ extracted in the decomposition side outlet. That is,

$$NH_3 \text{ conversion} = \frac{\dot{m}_{dec,NH_3}^I - \dot{m}_{dec,NH_3}^O}{\dot{m}_{dec,NH_3}^I}. \quad (33)$$

- The cell temperature.
- The cell voltage.

Next section summarizes some of the details of the multi-physics model, while additional details are provided as supplementary material.

3.1. Details of the multi-physics model

The computational fluid dynamics model was developed using COMSOL Multiphysics v6.1. The process involves multiple mass and energy exchange phenomena, including gas flow and diffusion in each chamber, ammonia cracking reactions, heat transport, and electrochemical interactions.

Gas flow is modeled using the Navier–Stokes equations, with corrections from the Brinkman equations to account for rapid fluid dynamics

Fig. 3. Main results of the CFD modeling of the electrochemical membrane reactor for the hydrogen generation with ammonia cracking reaction system. Further details on the CFD model can be found in the supplementary material, particularly in Fig. 1 and Table 4.

in porous media, where constituent particles are assumed to be spherical for permeability calculations. Gas diffusion is represented using an averaged-mixture approach based on Maxwell-Stefan equations, considering NH_3 , N_2 , H_2 , and H_2O in the internal chamber and H_2 , and H_2O in the external chamber, while neglecting Knudsen diffusion effects. The binary gas diffusion coefficient between steam and hydrogen is estimated using the Fuller equation, with a correction applied for porous domains based on the porosity-to-tortuosity ratio, assuming spherical particle geometry.

For heat transfer, the system is treated as adiabatic, with radiation effects neglected. Thermal conductivity within porous domains is adjusted based on estimated porosity. Notably, unlike the model presented in [19], this multi-physics model explicitly incorporates reaction kinetics as detailed in Section 2.4.1. All governing equations and material properties used in the simulation are fully documented in the supporting materials.

3.2. Results of the multi-physics model

The complete stack was modeled with a single cell-scale model including all the phenomena included on the process (Fig. 3 a and b). The model was simplified using a 2D axial symmetry model considering all the domains of the process for a 4 cm length cell (Fig. 3 c). Fig. 3 d shows the temperature profiles applying different current densities using the simulation conditions in Table 4. No large gradients are observed in the studied range of the current density. In fact, a difference of 15 °C can be observed between the areas with higher and lower temperature indicating a very uniform temperature along the reactor. It indicates that the hypothesis of uniform temperature in the cell can be considered for the proposed model. The hydrogen concentration and the NH_3 conversion profiles shows no significant radial gradients which may be associated with a limitation in extraction due to the good diffusion of H_2 . As a consequence, almost all the H_2 generated can be effectively extracted and validates the assumption that the porous media can be considered as a single control volume (Fig. 3 e and f).

The next subsections present 4 correlation studies between the proposed model and the multi-physics model.

3.3. Steady-state comparison

In this section, we are going to compare the equilibrium points obtained in both models with different sets of constant inputs. The parameters used in the model are depicted in Table 3, while the simulation conditions are depicted in Table 4. We highlight that, since the model in [19] does not contain any heat convection term, the heat transfer coefficient h_{ca} of the model has been fixed at zero.

Table 4
Simulation conditions.

Symbol	Description	Value	Units
$\dot{m}_{total,I,dec}$	Total input mass flow dec. side	$3.54 \cdot 10^{-6}$	kg s^{-1}
$y_{NH_3,I,dec}$	NH_3 mass fraction dec. side input	0.9	kg kg^{-1}
$\dot{m}_{H_2O,I,sweep}$	H_2O input mass flow sweep side	$3.95 \cdot 10^{-6}$	kg s^{-1}
P_{dec}^O	Outlet pressure dec. side	$2.5 \cdot 10^6$	Pa
P_{sweep}^O	Outlet pressure sweep side	$2.5 \cdot 10^6$	Pa
$T_{in,dec}$	Input temperature dec. side	600	°C
$T_{in,sweep}$	Input temperature sweep. side	600	°C

Fig. 4. Comparison of the H_2 extraction and lost at steady-state between the proposed model (SM, lines) and the multi-physics model (CFD, dots).

3.3.1. H_2 extraction/lost vs membrane current density

In the first case study, we compare the effects of the membrane current density I_{mem} on the H_2 extraction and the H_2 lost in the outlet. In order to separate the effect of this input on the indicators from other secondary processes, this scenario has been analyzed under isothermal conditions, that is, we assume a fixed cell temperature of 600 °C.

The results of the simulation are given in Fig. 4. As it can be seen, even considering the difference in complexity, the proposed model presents similar tendencies as the multi-physics one. Specifically, the proposed model effectively captures the linear growth of H_2 Extraction and the quadratic decline of H_2 Lost. Noticeably, there are larger errors at lower currents (approximately 0.073 of absolute error at 500 A m^{-2}) than at larger currents (approximately 0.01 of absolute error at 2900 A m^{-2}), in both, the H_2 Extraction and H_2 Lost. We highlight that this device should usually operate at relatively high current densities in order to maximize H_2 extraction and minimize H_2 lost. Thus, operating in the region where the proposed model is more accurate.

3.3.2. NH_3 conversion vs membrane current density

The second case scenario compares the effect of modifying the ammonia input mass flow in the decomposition side $\dot{m}_{q,i}^I$ and the membrane current I_{mem} to the NH_3 conversion. For the same reasons presented in the past section, this analysis has been conducted at isothermal conditions with a cell temperature of 600 °C. The result of the analysis is presented in Fig. 5. It can be observed that the proposed model accurately approximates the equilibrium points of the multi-physics model, with an absolute error below the 4%. The model accurately captures the decrease in ammonia conversion as the input mass flow increases. This behavior is physically consistent, as higher mass flow rates lead to quicker gas evacuation, reducing the residence time available for the reaction to occur.

3.3.3. Membrane voltage membrane current density

The third case scenario examines the effect of varying the membrane current density, I_{mem} , on the membrane voltage, $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$. As in the previous scenarios, isothermal conditions are assumed, with the cell operating at 600 °C. The results of this analysis are shown in Fig. 6. The proposed model successfully captures the relationship between current density and membrane voltage: specifically, the voltage increases with

Fig. 5. Comparison of the NH_3 conversion at different values of $m_{s,i}^I$ and I_{mem} between the proposed model (SM, lines) and the multi-physics model (CFD, dots).

Fig. 6. Comparison of the membrane voltage at different values of I_{mem} between the proposed model (SM, lines) and the multi-physics model (CFD, dots).

Fig. 7. Comparison of the cell temperature at different values of I_{mem} between the proposed model (SM, lines) and the multi-physics model (CFD, dots).

higher current density. Notably, at low current densities, the reversible voltage dominates and offsets the irreversible terms, resulting in a negative net voltage. The absolute error between the multiphysics model and the proposed model remains below 0.02 V throughout the range.

3.3.4. Cell temperature vs membrane current density

The last case scenario compares the effect of varying the membrane current density on the cell temperature. Precisely, we compare the cell temperature at equilibrium point of the proposed model with the temperature at the end of the cell provided by the multi-physics model. The results are depicted in Fig. 7. We can see that the absolute error is below 4 °C. Similar to the H_2 extraction/lost study, the accuracy of the model increases at high current densities, which should be the usual operating points of the device.

3.3.5. Discussion

The primary objective of this work is to develop a simplified version of the multi-physics model presented in [19], aimed at enabling the design of control-oriented algorithms, while preserving the essential accuracy of the original model.

A fundamental requirement for control algorithm design is that the model must be computable in real time, operating in parallel with the physical system. The proposed model satisfies this criterion by supporting faster-than-real-time simulation. For instance, as demonstrated in the following section, 500 s of system behavior can be simulated in under 150 s of computation time.

Achieving this computational performance necessitates certain simplifications to the original model. However, for control purposes, extremely high fidelity is not strictly required. What is essential is that the model accurately captures the key correlations and dynamic trends between inputs and outputs [23, Section 1.2]. In this section, we have shown that the proposed model successfully reproduces the primary relationships between critical inputs, such as input mass flow and current density, and relevant performance indicators. These relationships closely mirror those of the original multi-physics model. Therefore, we believe the proposed model offers strong practical value for control-oriented applications, combining computational efficiency with sufficient accuracy.

4. Application of the model: Monitoring of the hydrogen at the decomposition side

A safe and reliable operation for the PCER needs to include enough quantity of species in the porous media. One of the most important variables is the hydrogen partial pressure in the decomposition side. Indeed, a lack of hydrogen in the porous media combined with a large membrane current density may eventually induce starvation of the catalyst materials, which will accelerate the degradation of the system. For this reason, there is a need of monitoring the amount of hydrogen in the interior tube of the device.

Nonetheless, due to the structure of the device, there are currently no sensors capable of measuring in real-time the species concentration in the decomposition side. This fact motivates the design of algorithms that can estimate the quantity of specie in the device. In this section we will exploit the proposed model in order to design such algorithm. Naturally, the model proposed in this work is just an approximation of reality, thus, we cannot expect to derive an exact estimation of the species concentration from it. However, an estimation derived from the proposed model could be used as a qualitative indicator to detect if the device is operating inside or near starvation regions.

In this section, we propose an algorithm to estimate the partial pressure of hydrogen at the porous media control volume. The amount of hydrogen is a clear indicator that the device is not operating in an adequate region. For instance, low hydrogen conditions may appear due to a lack of ammonia in the decomposition side, too high current densities or low ammonia decomposition rates. We propose designing an observer [24] to achieve a real-time estimation of the variable. The details on the observer design are presented in the next section.

4.1. Observer design

For the development of the observer we will assume that the mixture total pressure in the sweep side, denoted as P_{sweep} , the temperature of the device T_{cell} and the voltage $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$ are measurable signals. Additionally, we will assume as measured inputs the mass flux of water in the sweep side $m_{sweep,\text{H}_2\text{O}}^I$, the pressure in the outlet, denoted as P_{sweep}^O , and the membrane current density I_{mem} .

We highlight that the decomposition side dynamics and the sweep side dynamics are only coupled by the hydrogen transfer across the membrane. Since we assumed that the temperature and current are directly measured, the term (10) is completely known. Consequently, we can separate the observer design problem from the sweep side and the decomposition side. Furthermore, as it will be shown in this section, the hydrogen mass fraction can be estimated by implementing an observer to the sweep side and using the voltage Eq. (21).

The main strategy followed in this section is to design an observer that uses the total pressure P_{sweep} , cell temperature T_{cell} and current density I_{mem} to estimate the value of mass fraction of hydrogen $y_{H_2,sweep}$ and the mixture density ρ_{sweep} . Then, $y_{H_2,sweep}$ and ρ_{sweep} can be used to compute the hydrogen partial pressure in the sweep side $p_{H_2,sweep}$ through the ideal gas law. Finally, the estimated $p_{H_2,sweep}$ and the measured membrane potential $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$ can be used to compute the partial pressure of hydrogen in the porous media through Eq. (21).

Precisely, the sweep side control volume contains two states, the mass fraction of hydrogen $y_{H_2,sweep}$ and the mixture density, ρ_{sweep} , which will be denoted here as

$$x = [x_1 \quad x_2]^T := [y_{H_2,sweep} \quad \rho_{sweep}]^T. \quad (34)$$

We assumed the total pressure in the sweep side and the cell temperature as measurable signals. Therefore, by dividing P_{sweep} by T_{cell} and using the ideal gas law we obtain the following measurable signal

$$y := \frac{P_{sweep}}{T_{cell}} = (k_1 - k_2)x_2x_1 + k_2x_2, \quad (35)$$

with $k_1 := R/M_{H_2}$ and $k_2 := R/M_{H_2O}$. Additionally, the control volume contains three measurable inputs, the input mass flow of H_2O , denoted as \dot{m}_{sweep,H_2O}^I , the flux of hydrogen across the membrane $\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2,s}$ and the pressure in the outlet, P_{sweep}^O . In this sense, the inputs will be denoted as

$$u = [u_1 \quad u_2 \quad u_3]^T = [\dot{m}_{sweep,H_2O}^I \quad \dot{m}_{sweep,H_2,s} \quad P_{sweep}^O]^T, \quad (36)$$

which will be assumed to be strictly positive. Taking this into account, the state-space model of the sweep side can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_1 \\ \dot{x}_2 \end{bmatrix} &= f(x, u) \\ &:= \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{k_3}{x_2} (-u_2 + x_1(u_1 + u_2)) \\ k_3(u_1 + u_2 - x_2k_4T_{cell}[(k_1 - k_2)x_2x_1 + k_2x_2 - u_3/T_{cell}]) \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

$$y = h(x) := k_2x_2 + (k_1 - k_2)x_2x_1,$$

where $k_3 := 1/V_{sweep}$, $k_4 := \pi r_{sweep}^4 / (8L_{sweep}\mu)$.

The observer design problem consists of finding a dynamic system of the form

$$\dot{\hat{x}} = j(\hat{x}, y, u), \quad (38)$$

where the estimated state is \hat{x} and the vector field j has to be designed. The objective is to ensure that, for any initial conditions $x(0)$ and $\hat{x}(0)$ of the observer (38) and plant to be observed, the estimation error vanishes asymptotically, i.e.,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|x(t) - \hat{x}(t)\| = 0. \quad (39)$$

In other words, an observer is an algorithm that uses the measured signals y and u to generate an estimation \hat{x} that asymptotically converges to the true values x . More details on these algorithms can be found in [24].

It is noticeable that the system (37) is strongly nonlinear, this makes the observer design problem non-trivial. One possible solution to this challenge is to approximate the system using the first-order terms of the Taylor expansion and then incorporate a linear observer into the resulting dynamics. A common example of this technique is the Extended Kalman Filter (EKF). However, this approach assumes that higher-order terms of the Taylor expansion can be neglected, which is not always valid across the entire domain of the PCER model. As a result, this approximation introduces additional modeling errors, leading to reduced accuracy and potential instability of EKFs in electrochemical systems [25]. Therefore, there is a clear need for observers that explicitly account for the system's nonlinear dynamics.

In this sense, sliding-mode observers [26] and high-gain observers [27] are typical nonlinear observer techniques to be used in these scenarios, as exemplified by similar estimation problems in other electrochemical devices [28–31]. The applicability of these observers rely on one fact: that there is a one-to-one map that relates the measured output and its derivatives to the states of the system. Under this property, the sliding-mode or the high-gain observer techniques are based on a two-step process. First, an observer is implemented to estimate the derivatives of the measured output. Second, the one-to-one map that relates the measured output derivatives and the states is inverted in order to recover the states. Unfortunately, for system (37), the map $(y, \dot{y}) \rightarrow (x_1, x_2)$ is ill-conditioned due to the difference in scale between x_1 and x_2 , which could potentially lead to numerical issues during practical implementation of sliding-mode or high-gain observers. This motivates the design of alternative and more unconventional observer.

For the design of the observer we will exploit the fact that the states x and the inputs u are strictly positive and bounded. Consequently, the states are expected to evolve within a compact set $\mathcal{X} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}^2$, while the controlled inputs, are defined within another compact set $\mathcal{U} \subseteq \mathbb{R}_{>0}^3$. Under this assumption, the proposed observer takes the following form

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\hat{x}}_1 \\ \dot{\hat{x}}_2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{k_3}{\hat{x}_2} (-u_2 + \hat{x}_1(u_1 + u_2)) \\ k_3(u_1 + u_2 - \hat{x}_2k_4T_{cell}[y - u_3/T_{cell}]) \end{bmatrix}, \quad (40)$$

and we assume $\hat{x}_1(0), \hat{x}_2(0) > 0$.

The convergence of the observer can guaranteed if

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^t \Delta P_q(s) ds = \infty. \quad (41)$$

That is, in average, the pressure inside the sweep side of the device is larger than the outside. This is not a restrictive assumption, since the device should operate in this mode in order to extract hydrogen from the device. In particular, we can assume $\Delta P_q(s) > 0$.

Precisely, in such scenario, for the case where the model exactly describes the true system, we have that (39) is satisfied for any initial condition $\hat{x}(0), x(0) \in \mathcal{X}$. The proof of the observer convergence is given in the supplementary material.

4.2. Hydrogen partial pressure estimation

Once the observer provides an accurate estimation of the sweep side hydrogen mass fraction \hat{x}_1 and the gas mixture density \hat{x}_2 we can accurately estimate the hydrogen partial pressure by inverting the voltage Eq. (21). Precisely, the hydrogen partial pressure, denoted here as $\hat{p}_{H_2,dec}$, can be obtained through the following equation:

$$\hat{p}_{H_2,dec} = \hat{p}_{H_2,sweep} \exp\left(-\frac{2F(\Delta\Phi_{mem} - ASR I_{mem})}{RT_{cell}}\right) \quad (42)$$

where ASR is the corrected area specific resistance, computed through (24), $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$ is the membrane potential and $\hat{p}_{H_2,sweep}$ is the estimation of the hydrogen partial pressure at the sweep side, which can be computed by means of the ideal gas law and the estimation of the observer previously presented as follows:

$$\hat{p}_{H_2,sweep} = \frac{\hat{x}_1 \hat{x}_2 RT_{cell}}{M_{H_2}}. \quad (43)$$

4.3. Real-time estimation of the area specific resistance

Noticeably, the accuracy of Eq. (42) directly depends on the accuracy of the voltage Eq. (21). In this sense, even if the partial pressure in the sweep side was estimated exactly, an inaccurate voltage equation will lead up to a non-reliable hydrogen partial pressure estimation.

With this in mind, we highlight that the voltage Eq. (21) has one parameter that may be difficult to be measured in practice. We are referring to the area specific resistance at nominal conditions, ASR^0 .

The value of this parameter depends on various factors such as the phase volume ratios of its components [32]. Therefore, one may expect significant variations on this parameter between different PCERs. The purpose of this section is to propose an online algorithm to estimate this parameter.

Let us recall the voltage Eq. (21). The objective is to design an algorithm that based on the measurements of the voltage $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$, the temperature T_{cell} and the current I_{mem} , can estimate the unknown area specific resistance at nominal conditions, ASR^0 . We highlight that this problem is not solvable for all possible operating conditions of the system, since the term E_{rev} is usually unknown. For instance, if the system were to operate in an equilibrium point, then, multiple combinations of values for E_{rev} and ASR_0 , may generate the same $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$. In order to avoid such scenario, we are going to actively modify the variable I_{mem} to recover the observability of E_{rev} and ASR^0 .

Precisely, consider that we introduce the following current signal in the system and the rest of the inputs are maintained constant

$$I_{mem} = u_c + s_b, \quad s_b := \kappa s \left(\frac{t}{\varepsilon} \right), \quad (44)$$

where $u_c \in \mathbb{R}$ is a nominal current value of the cell. We assume u_c to be constant and $s_b \in \mathbb{R}$ is a signal of high-frequency, with $s(\cdot) : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ being a periodic function with zero mean, $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ is a small function that ‘‘scales’’ the frequency of the signal and $\kappa \in \mathbb{R}$ is a scaling function of the signal s_b . The intuition behind such a signal is that, while the voltage $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$ and the terms multiplying I_{mem} in (21) are affected by the high-frequency term s_b , the reversible voltage E_{rev} will be mostly unaffected by s_b due to the low-pass behavior of the system.

More precisely, following a second-order averaging analysis [33] it can be concluded that for a sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$ the reversible voltage will converge to the following signal

$$E_{rev} = \bar{E}_{rev} + \kappa\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \quad (45)$$

where \bar{E}_{rev} is the constant reversible voltage obtained in the equilibrium point associated with the current density $I_{mem} = u_c$, and $\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ is a factor that reduces with ε .

With this in mind, the voltage Eq. (21) reduces to the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\Phi_{mem} &= \bar{E}_{rev} + ASR^0 \exp\left(\frac{E_{mem}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_{cell}} - \frac{1}{1073} \right]\right) I_{mem} + \kappa\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon) \\ &= \Psi^\top \theta + \kappa\mathcal{O}(\varepsilon), \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where we have defined

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \exp\left(\frac{E_{mem}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_{cell}} - \frac{1}{1073} \right]\right) s_b \end{bmatrix}^\top \\ \theta &= \begin{bmatrix} \bar{E}_{rev} + ASR^0 \exp\left(\frac{E_{mem}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_{cell}} - \frac{1}{1073} \right]\right) u_c \\ ASR^0 u_c \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

Notice that the voltage equation in (46) can be rearranged to an equation linear in the variables θ , where Ψ is a measured time varying vector and θ is a vector of constant parameters to be estimated

The term $ASR^0 \exp\left(\frac{E_{mem}}{R} \left[\frac{1}{T_{cell}} - \frac{1}{1073} \right]\right) u_c$ is assumed to be constant even though it depends on the temperature. We can make this assumption, because the high-frequency components in s_b will have a minimal effect on the temperature. This is a reasonable assumption, at least, when the PCER has reached a steady-state.

Now, we can implement multiple algorithms to estimate in real-time the unknown parameters, that is the vector θ , in (46) [34]. In this work, we focus on the algorithm proposed in [35], which have also been used in similar electrochemical systems [36]. More precisely, the estimator consists in the following set of dynamics,

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\eta} &= \alpha_1 \Omega \Psi (\Delta\Phi_{mem} - \Psi^\top \eta), \quad \eta(0) = [0 \quad 0 \quad 0]^\top, \\ \dot{\Omega} &= -\alpha_1 \Psi \Psi^\top \Omega, \quad \Omega(0) = I_3 \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where I_3 is the identity matrix of order 3, $\alpha_1 > 0$ is a parameter to be tuned, $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\Omega \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 3}$. Based on the solution of (48) a new signal, y_{pd} , and a new regressor vector Ψ_{pd} are computed as follows

$$\begin{aligned} y_{pd} &= \text{adj}\{I_3 - \Omega\} \eta \\ \Psi_{pd} &= \det\{I_3 - \Omega\}, \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

where $\det\{\cdot\}$ is the determinant and $\text{adj}\{\cdot\}$ is the adjugate. We highlight that the operation (49) serve to diagonalize the matrix Ω . It was shown in [37] that this diagonalization process improves the performance of the parameter estimation algorithm.

The last part of the algorithm consists of using the new signals y_{pd} , Ψ_{pd} in a standard gradient descent dynamics. More precisely,

$$\dot{\hat{\theta}} = \Gamma \Psi_{pd} (y_{pd} - \Psi_{pd}^\top \hat{\theta}), \quad (50)$$

where Γ is the adaptation gain of the estimator. Now, we consider that the estimator (50) generates an adequate estimation, if for any initial condition the following property is satisfied or the case that the sensors present some noise we can ensure practical convergence, denoted as

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |\hat{\theta}(t) - \theta| \leq \varepsilon_\theta \quad (51)$$

where ε_θ is a positive constant that considers potential sensor noise. More common real-time parameter estimators [38] can guarantee the convergence (51) if the vector Ψ is bounded and satisfies a **persistence of excitation** condition. In particular, the system needs to satisfy for all $t > 0$ and some positive constants $T, \alpha > 0$

$$\int_t^{t+T} \Psi(\tau) \Psi(\tau)^\top d\tau > \alpha I. \quad (52)$$

Unfortunately, satisfying the persistence of excitation condition (52) is undesirable in the considered problem, since it requires a value $s_b \neq 0$ for all time, which is equivalent to introduce the signal (44) persistently on the system. This will unnecessarily increase the degradation of the system and increase the electric consumption of the system. The proposed estimator avoids this issue, because it can guarantee the convergence (51) under the less restrictive condition of **interval excitation**. Precisely, a bounded signal $\Psi(t) \in \mathbb{R}^q$ is said to be intervally excited if there exists a constant $t_c > 0$ such that

$$\int_0^{t_c} \Psi(\tau) \Psi(\tau)^\top d\tau > 0. \quad (53)$$

We highlight that persistence of excitation only requires applying the current (44) for a finite time, which is more reasonable in the considered system.

4.4. Numerical simulation

In this section, the performance of the proposed observer is validated in a numerical simulation. In this simulation, the model presented and validated in Section 2 has been used as the ground truth. That is, in the numerical simulation, the PCER model was excited by some particular set of inputs to generate the signals P_{sweep} , T_{cell} , current I_{mem} and $\Delta\Phi_{mem}$. Then, these signals were implemented in the proposed observer scheme to generate an estimation of the hydrogen partial pressure on the porous media $\hat{p}_{H_2, BZCY}$ and the area specific resistance of the membrane at nominal conditions, ASR^0 .

The parameters of the PCER model are specified in Table 3 and the simulation conditions are specified in Table 4. The input current has been fixed as in (44) with the nominal value $u_c = 2000$ [A m⁻²] and, during the first 100 s, $\kappa = 2 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $\varepsilon = 1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ and $s(\cdot) = \sin(\cdot)$. After the first 100 s, the current is fixed to the nominal value, that is, $s_b = 0$. The evolution of this current can be seen in the top-left of Fig. 8.

As it can be seen in Fig. 8, the high-frequency term s_b has no significant effect on the temperature of the cell, the voltage and the pressure of the sweep, which validates Eq. (45). We highlight that, since the term s_b is zero in most of the simulation, the persistence of excitation condition (52) is not satisfied. Nonetheless, the parameters have

Fig. 8. (Top-left) Evolution of the current density at around 100 s. (Top-right) Evolution of the membrane voltage. (Bottom-left) Evolution of the cell temperature. (Bottom-right) Evolution of the pressure in the sweep side.

Fig. 9. (Top) Value of the ASR^0 for the ground truth model (blue) and evolution of the estimation (red). (Bottom) Evolution of the ground truth partial pressure of hydrogen in the porous media (blue) and evolution of the observer estimation (red). (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

been selected such that interval excitation condition (53) is satisfied. Naturally, varying the parameters u_c , κ , and ε results in different signal profiles in Fig. 8. However, what truly matters is not the particular shape of these profiles, but the ability of the estimation algorithm to accurately determine ASR^0 and $p_{H_2,BZCY}$, which is discussed below.

The parameters of the estimator (48) have been fixed to $\alpha_1 = 1$ and $\Gamma = 1$, to obtain an adequate convergence rate. Fig. 9 compares the estimation of the proposed algorithm and the value provided by the ground truth model. The rest of the parameters of the estimation algorithm are the ones in Table 3, except for the parameter ASR^0 which is assumed to be unknown.

As the figure shows, even if the initial conditions from the estimation algorithm and the ground truth model are completely different, the algorithm can correct for this discrepancy and obtain a consistent estimation of the ASR^0 and the partial pressure of hydrogen in the porous media, which validates the result.

5. Conclusions

In this work, we presented a control-oriented and computational efficient model of a single cell of the PCER presented in [19]. The model has been validated by comparison to the multi-physics model presented in [19]. Then, the proposed model has been used to develop a soft sensor of the hydrogen partial pressure in the decomposition side porous media and the corrected area specific resistance of the membrane at nominal conditions. The proposed soft sensor has been validated in a numerical simulations. Future works will focus on two directions. First, extending the control-oriented model and the proposed soft sensor to a stack level. Second, based on these models and soft sensors, develop control algorithms that guarantees optimality, safety and reliability of the PCER device.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Andreu Cecilia: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **David Catalán-Martínez:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Sonia Escolástico:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Project administration. **Maria Serra:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Jose M. Serra:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Ramon Costa-Castelló:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2025.150557>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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